

SEMIOTICS IN TEACHING SYSTEMS OF LINEAR EQUATIONS: CONVERSIONS AND TREATMENTS

 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10511668

Lucas Gabriel Silva Rodrigues de Jesus

Professor, Graduated in Mathematics. lucas.rodrigues.jesus@escola.pr.gov.br

Fernanda de Araújo

Teacher, Graduated in Mathematics. fer.gerrard@homail.com

Magna Natalia Marin Pires

Professor, PhD in Mathematics Teaching. magna@uel.br

ABSTRACT

This work is an experiential report implemented within the Pedagogical Residency Program, a governmental project by the Coordination for the Improvement of Higher Education Personnel (CAPES), conducted in the Mathematics course at the State University of Londrina - Campus Londrina/PR, Brazil. The project took place in a 1st-year class of the public high school system in the same municipality, with the aim of teaching Linear Systems (Existence and Uniqueness of solution). The activity's construction and theoretical contributions were prompted by discussions on contextualization, encompassing social contextualization, pseudo-contextualization, and meaningful contextualization. These perspectives have implications for classroom practices. To achieve this goal, a sequence of mathematical tasks was developed and implemented, methodologically supported by Raymond Duval's Theory of Registers of Representation. The pedagogical tool employed was the GeoGebra software, a free platform for algebraic and geometric visualization and manipulation tools. The tasks aimed to transition between natural, algebraic, and geometric languages through the author's semiotic treatment and conversions. The report details the development of each task, discussing each step and the invested pedagogical intentions, summarizing semiotic actions in a framework. It was concluded that learning mathematical signs is only realized through approaches that construct meanings, as exemplified in this production, highlighting mathematics itself as a rich contextual source when used, for instance, with a semiotic approach.

Keywords: GeoGebra. Semiotics. System of Linear Equations.

INTRODUCTION

In the classroom context, engaging students in developing a mathematical activity makes mathematical learning more attractive and meaningful. Thus, for meaningful learning,

the relationship between mathematics and context is highly recommended, so that students can ascend from the concrete to the abstract. However, the aspect of contextualization is confused in the literature and in teaching practice, among others.

According to Pinheiro and Ostermann (pg. 3, 2010) “contextualized knowledge is that which manifests itself in a situation, in a set of relationships with a specific environment that completes its meaning”. Contextualization in mathematics teaching encompasses three facets, namely: social contextualization, pseudo-contextualization and meaningful contextualization. As for the first, contextualization is understood as the movement of 'removing' something from the student's daily life and 'taking' it to the classroom, or even as something emerging from the student's reality. Almeida, Benedito and Vieira (2020), where they cite Spinelli (2011), highlight that there is a foolishness in recognizing what constitutes context, due to an exaggerated apology that everything must be brought to the student's reality. This exaggeration prevents the student from truly understanding the content, as it goes beyond the adopted context.

It is noted that, due to the emphasis on contextualization focused on the students' daily reality, the selection of content, within the students' repertoire, is impoverished. As a result, there is a tendency to neglect the approach to content that is not easily contextualized within these parameters.

As for the second, pseudo-contextualization, mathematical knowledge is perceived through a hypothetical story. It is the practice of presenting situations that appear to be from the real world, but that have no genuine or meaningful connection to the mathematical concepts in question. This can lead to a superficial or misunderstanding of the concepts, as students may not be able to make a real application of them. Almeida, Benedito and Vieira (2020), where they cite Paula et al. (2017), states that the promotion of pseudo contextualization consists of the conception that all mathematics content must be contextualized. However, what ends up occurring are situations that portray something unreal, serving as a pretext for presenting the data.

Pinheiro and Ostermann (2010) classify pseudo-contextualization into two types. The first would be when the question is formulated in terms of specific objects, just to give concreteness to abstract concepts, but does not describe a situation that justifies this choice. Therefore, it does not make it essential for understanding the issue. (Lopes et al., 2018) exemplifies how “John has many cups and puts 1 bean in the first cup, 2 in the second, 3 in the third and so on. How many beans will be placed in the 2000th cup?” The second type is when the question appears disconnected from the context, so the situation described does not contribute to understanding the question and is not necessary to reach the correct answer.

“Joãozinho did a test where there was the following question: Determine the roots of $x^2 - 5x + 6 = 0$ ”. (Lopes, et al., 2018).

As for the third, meaningful contextualization, Almeida, Benedito and Vieira (2020), where they quote Santos et al (2017), highlight the idea that context should not be addressed only with elements that the teacher considers to be part of the student's daily life. It is necessary to consider the possibility of constructing meanings based on internal mathematics issues, as a result of which there will be no discarding of content that, apparently, does not have concrete and immediate applicability .

This article reports the experience of the first two authors of this report, graduates of the Mathematics Degree course at the State University of Londrina (UEL/PR), guided by the third author in the Pedagogical Residency Program.

The authors developed and executed a lesson plan, developed in the thematic axis of Algebra, Systems of Linear Equations, from a semiotic perspective, with the methodological strategy of Exploratory Teaching, enhanced with the use of GeoGebra *software* . The planning was applied to two classes of the 1st Year A and B of High School at a state public school in the city of Londrina, PR (Brazil). For this report we chose to describe moments that occurred in class A.

Supported by the importance of representations, mathematical investigations and the use of technology, we present the specific objectives of the tasks: a) Graphically represent a first degree equation using GeoGebra; b) Graphically interpret the solutions of a system of equations. c) Recognize, based on graphic representations, possible (determined and indeterminate) and impossible systems. Relate to parallels, competitors and coincidents.

THEORETICAL FOUNDATION

Duval (p. 14, 2009) states that “one cannot have understanding in mathematics if we do not distinguish an object and its representation”. In this sense, Dreyfus (1991) states that

[...] representation and abstraction are, then, complementary processes in opposite directions: on the one hand, a concept is often abstracted from several of its representations and, on the other hand, representations are always representations of a more abstract concept. When a single representation of a concept is used, attention may be focused on it rather than the abstract object. However, when several representations are used in parallel, the relationship with the corresponding abstract concept becomes important. (Dreyfus, 1991, p. 38).

Duval (apud Moretti 2002, p.349) determines that “the (integral) understanding of a

conceptual content rests on the coordination of two registers of two representation registers at the same time and this coordination is manifested by the speed and spontaneity of the cognitive activity of conversion"

Duval (2005, apud Santos 2009, p. 58), defines semiotic representation as: semiotic representations are productions constituted by the use of signs (signals) belonging to a representation system that have their own difficulties of significance and functioning. A figure, a statement in natural language, an algebraic formula, a graph, are semiotic representations that highlight different semiotic systems.

Duval (2006) also defines two totally different types of semiotic activities: treatment and conversion. The first is a transformation of representations carried out within the same register and, the second, consists of changing from one register to another without changing the mathematical objects that are at stake.

METHODOLOGY

The methodological approach chosen is exploratory. The choice will be made because, as the work is described as an experience report, it indicates an investigation based on the author's practical experience in the Pedagogical Residency Program. Ponte, Pereira and Martins (2021, pg. 3) argue that

The exploratory approach, close to the *inquiry-based approach*, is a teaching approach that leaves "an important part of the work of discovery and construction of knowledge for students to carry out" (Ponte, 2005, p. 13). The work in class involves a challenging task and students are involved in activities to explore mathematical concepts and ideas, which allows them to reflect on these activities and, in this way, learn (Ponte; Branco; Quaresma, 2014). It is therefore an approach that, like the *inquiry-based approach*, has the potential to "promote understanding of concepts, critical thinking and positive attitudes (of students) towards science" (Krämer; Nessler; Schlüter, 2015, p. 326), but it is complex, requiring careful planning.

Ponte, Pereira and Martins (2021), structure the approach into three moments: (i) proposal of a task; (ii) students' autonomous work; and (iii) collective discussion and final synthesis. First, the teacher proposes a task to the students and ensures that everyone understands and interprets it correctly. In the second stage, students work independently, individually or in small groups, and the teacher monitors this work in order to identify the students' resolution strategies, the mistakes they are making and the difficulties they are experiencing, supporting them without reduce the degree of challenge of the task. Finally, the

teacher selects some resolutions that he considers interesting to discuss with the whole class, sequences them, and asks students to explain and justify their answers.

REPORT OF ACTIVITIES

Task 1

Lucas bought 3 pens and 2 pencils paying R\$7.20. Danilo bought 2 pens and 1 pencil paying R\$4.40. The system of 1st degree equations that best represents the situation is:	
$\begin{cases} x + y = 3,60 \\ x - y = 2,20 \end{cases}$ The)	$\begin{cases} 3x + 2y = 7,20 \\ 2x + y = 4,40 \end{cases}$ w)
$\begin{cases} 3x + y = 7,20 \\ x + y = 4,40 \end{cases}$ B)	$\begin{cases} 3x - 2y = 7,20 \\ 2x - y = 4,40 \end{cases}$ d)

Source: the authors (2023)

The choice of alternatives in the task aims to give students, who have not learned algebraic expressions or linear equations, a chance to use other logical processes to correctly identify the linear system. And as expected, when questioned about the choice, many associated the value of the pen with x and y , with the pen, as they recognized the coefficients of the equations and fixed them to the objects. There are only two options left: c) and d). In this case, it was explained that the values R\$7.20 and R\$4.40 are the accumulated values of the items; that is, they are represented through the sum of the values of pencils and pens.

In the course of the task, we highlight that x : unit value of the pen; y : unit value of the pencil. That is, the unknowns are responsible for representing the unit values of the pen and pencil, and not their quantities; in this case, these are expressed as the coefficients of the monomials of the linear equations.

The quantity of items is forwarded as follows: if the value of a pen unit is represented by x , maintaining the unit value, for two pens, we have twice the value of the unit, that is, $2x$ and so on. against. And similarly, we have the representation of the price for the pencil. In this way, the first semiotic action carried out by the students was conversion; that is, the algebraic representation given to natural language.

Another relevant aspect concerns the choice of representations of the unknowns x and y . It could be easily used can and l , respectively for the values of pens and pencils; however, aiming at geometric exploration, in the *software*, a semiotic treatment action was carried out in relation to the exchange of unknowns.

Task 2

- a) Plot the graph of the system of equations that describes the previous situation.
- b) The lines associated with the equations meet at some point, what is the coordinate of this point (value assigned to x and y)?
- c) Solve the system of equations using one of the methods presented in class (addition, substitution or others). What is the system solution?
- d) What is the relationship between the solution of the system and the meeting point of the straight lines?

Source: the authors (2023)

To discuss the term “plot”, we relied on the Houaiss Electronic Dictionary, which presented “adaptation of the English verb " *to plot* ", ' to make a graph, map or plan of; mark or annotate on a chart or map; Locate using coordinates, etc. ”

GeoGebra software was introduced ; it was noted that none of the students were familiar with the platform; In this way, they were assisted in using basic tools, such as how to navigate the linear system when entering the *software*. The linear system indicated in alternative c), of task 1, was then plotted.

Figure 1 - Students exploring the GeoGebra program

Source: the authors (2023)

The first semiotic activity of this task refers to the conversion of the algebraic language from the linear system to its geometric representation, which was presented with two straight lines. Notoriously, students associated the two representations; that is, they constituted the sign. Almost immediately, they questioned the meaning of that construction. It was explained that the lines are straight due to the proportionality between the quantity of items purchased, pens and pencils, and their respective values. In other words, when purchasing two pens, the amount to be paid is double the value of one, and so on, considering that, regardless of the quantity, the value of each object is unique.

The second semiotic activity refers to the conversion of the algebraic solution of the equation system to its geometric representation, this as the point of intersection between the two straight lines, associated with the linear system. The students were instructed to look for the “point” tool and use it by clicking on the point where the lines compete. After representing this point, students noticed a new entry on the left side of the program (1.6,1.2) *interface* :

The resident explored on the blackboard the exchange of the unknowns, x and y , in the linear system, with the values 1.6 and 1.2. Next, there is the semiotic conversion of the representation of the coordinates of the point of competition between the straight lines and the solution of the linear system:

(i) $3 \cdot (1,60) + 2 \cdot (1,20) = 4,8 + 2,40 = 7,20.$

(ii) $2 \cdot (1,60) + 1,20 = 3,20 + 1,20 = 4,40.$

Where (i) and (ii) represent, respectively, the linear equations of the described system.

Figure 2 - Geometric representation of the straight lines from task 1

Source: the authors (2023)

Task 3

Plot the graph for each system of equations below. Check if there are meeting points between the straight lines. What can we say about the solutions?

a)
$$\begin{cases} x + y = 10 \\ 20x + 5y = 140 \end{cases}$$

b)
$$\begin{cases} 2x + y = 5 \\ 4x + 2y = 10 \end{cases}$$

c)
$$\begin{cases} 3x + 7y = 3 \\ 3x + 7y = 45 \end{cases}$$

Source: the authors (2023)

It is pertinent to say that this task takes advantage of the context of linear systems, not related, for now, to the purchase of pens and pencils. Contextual change does not imply the absence of meanings; but rather the exchange of meaning operators; that is, for the levels to pass: the sign, meaning and abstraction, the concrete object needed to take another form; in this case, the very concept of linear systems.

At this stage, in addition to formalizing the concepts, we were concerned with promoting deeper analyzes involving the existence and uniqueness of linear systems solutions, as well as the conversion of the semiotic representations of the concept. Next, the definition of linear system solutions is recorded. Kolmann and Hill (2014, p. 29), argue that “every system of linear equations has either no solution, or exactly one, or an infinite number of solutions”. It follows from this finding that a linear system can be classified into three types: possible and determined system (SPD) and possible and indeterminate system (SPI) and impossible system (SI).

The three items were discussed separately, in order to attribute definitions to the constructions made. In the first item, students' autonomy was noted in semiotic conversions from algebraic language to geometric language, as well as the use of the program's tools. As an action to prove the geometric solution, residents assigned the values of the coordinates of the point of competition between the lines to the values of the unknowns x and y . Below is the transposition of the blackboard record to the digital format expressed in this article:

i) $6 + 4 = 10$.

ii) $20 \cdot (6) + 5(4) = 140 \Rightarrow 120 + 20 = 140$.

Figure 3 - equation of competing lines and their geometric representations

Source: the authors (2023)

Regarding the second system of equations of this task, the students instantly performed the semiotic conversion and soon after came across two straight lines superimposed on each other. The question was asked: “what is the meeting point between these straight lines?”. The students were told that, when there was competition between the lines at a single point, the coordinates of the point were the corresponding solutions; In this case, it would have to be similar, as the lines are coincident, so they have infinite points in common, which would result in infinite solutions. Thus, for proof, in a similar way to the previous system, several solutions of the linear system were tested on the board.

Figure 4 - equation of coincident lines and their geometric representations

Source: the authors (2023)

The second linear system discussed initiated the second semiotic activity. This activity converts the representation from geometric language to algebraic language. The coefficients of the system of equations were expressed, respectively (i) 2, 1 and 5 and (ii) 4, 5 and 10. It was explained that using the multiplicative principle, when performing the product of the coefficients by the number two, would result in the second equation. In this way, the geometric relationship of infinite solutions is evidenced by the proportionality between the equations.

Regarding the third system of equations of this task, immediately after the geometric representation of the linear equations, the students noticed that there was no solution for the system. The absence of a solution, the second semiotic activity, was conducted in a similar way to the previous item, first exposing the coefficients of the equations, respectively (i) 3, 7 and 3 and (ii) 3, 7 and 45. It was exposed that the coefficients of the monomials $3x$ and $7y$ are proportional, if the product with the number one is used. However, the difference between the equations is evidenced by the independent terms 3 and 45, which do not fit the same multiplicative principle. Therefore, highlighting the non-existence of a geometric solution with the semiotic treatment of the algebraic representation of the system's equations.

Figure 5 - Equation of parallel lines and their geometric representations

Source: the authors (2023)

Table 1 - Semiotic activities carried out in the tasks

Tasks	Semiotic Conversions	Actions
Task 1	Natural Language ⇒ Algebraic Language	(i) conversion of natural language to algebraic representation; (ii) treatment of algebraic language.
Task 2	Algebraic Language ⇒ Geometric Language	(i) conversion of the algebraic language from the system of equations of two unknowns to the geometric representation of two concurrent lines. (ii) conversion of the algebraic language from the solution of the system of linear equations to the geometric representation of the point of competition between the lines; (iii) treatment of the geometric representation of straight lines by the proportionality of the values of pens and pencils.
Task 3	Algebraic Language ⇒ Geometric Language ⇒ Algebraic Language	(i) conversion of the algebraic representation of the linear system to the geometric representation; (ii) conversion and treatment of the proportionality of the coefficients of the equations of linear systems and the existence and uniqueness of the solutions.

Source: the authors (2023)

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The work carried out showed that the attribution of meanings goes beyond the conception of contextualization as events in students' daily lives. It was evident that mathematics itself can be used as a contextualization tool; in this case, with the semiotic perspective.

The digital platform was used not only as an engagement mechanism, but as a pedagogical instrument, as it was a means of spreading knowledge and enhanced the development of the semiotic work of mathematical tasks. This evidence opposes conservative innovation, a very common practice in classrooms.

Teaching mathematics involves a multiplicity of responsibilities, since, by exploring different languages, such as natural, algebraic and geometric, students are able to escape the limitations inherent to mathematical language when it is confined to a single form of representation.

Therefore, initial teacher training must assume responsibility for these discussions, since, in the case of ambiguities in the scientific community and, consequently, in classroom practice, as occurs with the concept of contextualization, epistemological limitations end up manifesting themselves in the context of both the teacher and the students.

The Pedagogical Residency program played a fundamental role in the clear development of the project, representing a truly enriching joint collaboration.

REFERENCES

ALMEIDA, HMDS; VIEIRA, SL; BENEDITO, RCS Pseudo Contextualization in Mathematics: A Current Problem. Perform. oct. 2020 Maceió AL. Available at: <
https://editorarealize.com.br/editora/anais/conedu/2020/TRABALHO_EV140_MD1_SA13_ID986_24082020144650.pdf> Accessed on: 29 Nov. 2023.

DREYFUS, T. (1991). Advanced Mathematical Thinking Processes. In D. Tall (Ed.), Advanced Mathematical Thinking (pp. 25-41). Dordrecht: Kluwer Academic Publisher.

DUVAL, R. **Semiosis and human thought** : Semiotic records and intellectual learning. Trans. Lênio Fernandes Levy and Marisa Rosâni Abreu Silveira. São Paulo: Editora Livraria da Physics, 2009.

DUVAL, R. (2006). Quelle semiotique pour l'analyse de la activité et des productions 'mathématiques? *Revista Latinoamericana de Investigación en Matemática Educativa*, 9 (Extra 1), 45-82.
https://www.scielo.org.mx/scielo.php?script=sci_nlinks&ref=6784035&pid=S1665-2436201200020000200011&lng=es

KOLMANN, Bernard; HILL, David R. **Introduction to linear algebra**: with applications. Translated by Alessandra Bosquilha. 8. ed. Rio de Janeiro: LTC, 2014.

LOPES, Thiago Beirigo; ALVES, Ana Cláudia Tasinaffo; LEÃO, Marcelo Franco; DUTRA, Mara Maria. Analysis regarding pseudo-contextualization in the tests of the first phase of the last three editions of OBMEP (2015-2017). *Kiri-Kerê*, v. 4, p. 66-93, 2018. Available at: <
<https://periodicos.ufes.br/kirikere/article/view/17672/13607>> . Accessed on: 17 Oct. 2023.

MARTINS, M.; PEREIRA, JM; PONTE, JP The Challenges of the Exploratory Approach in Teaching Mathematics: learning from two future teachers through lesson study. *Bolema*, Rio Claro (SP), v. 35, no. 69, p. 343-364, apr. 2021. Available at: <
<https://www.scielo.br/j/bolema/a/HjpPFXmM7V9bWq8MKmcSkxt/?format=pdf&lang=pt>> . Accessed on: 20 Oct. 2023.

MORETTI, Mércles T. The role of representation registers in Mathematics learning. *Counterpoints*, Itajaí, v. 2, no. 6, p. 343-362, Dec. 2002. Available at: <
<https://siaiap32.univali.br/seer/index.php/rc/article/download/180/152>> . Accessed on: 10 Oct. 2023.

PINHEIRO, NC; OSTERMANN, F. A comparative analysis of physics questions in the new ENEM and in university entrance exams with regard to the concepts of interdisciplinarity and contextualization. In: *Research Meeting on Physics Teaching*, 12, Águas de Lindóia, 2010. Anais. Águas de Lindóia: Brazilian Physics Society, 2010. p.1-13. Available at: <

http://www.if.ufrgs.br/ensfis_fernanda/arquivos/publicacoes/nathan_fernanda_xii_epef_2010.pdf > Accessed on: 29 Nov. 2023.

SANTOS, Cintia Aparecida Bento dos; CURI, Edda. Some aspects of articulation between theories of French didactics and their contributions to teacher training. REVEMAT - Electronic Education Magazine v. 4 n. 1 (2009) . Available at: <
<https://periodicos.ufsc.br/index.php/revemat/article/view/1981-1322.2009v4n1p53/12160> >
Accessed on: 27 Oct. 2023.